

INTERLAMINAR STRESSES IN CORRUGATED STRUCTURES MADE FROM ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Corrugated laminated sheets have been used in morphing wing design, since they provide deformation of the wing skin in chord direction while they behave very stiff in the span direction at low weight. For larger thickness-to-periodic-length ratios interlaminar stresses and hence the risk of delamination increase in the laminate. Interlaminar stresses are influenced by material anisotropy as well as geometry. An investigation of these parameters is crucial in order to find concepts to reduce the risk of delamination. The present work studies the influence of the laminate-thickness to periodic-cell-length ratio, material anisotropy degree and the corrugation-amplitude to periodic-cell-length ratio on the interlaminar shear and through-thickness stress. Two midface-shapes are considered: the one is sinusoidal and the other consists of two circular sections.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research has proven that morphing wing solutions can improve the control and flight performance with no or low weight penalty in comparison with conventional airplanes [1], [2]. Thill et al. [3] investigated different morphing skin solutions and stated that the main characteristic to be looked for morphing skins is an element of strong anisotropy. The anisotropy is required to allow good compliance in chordwise direction. This guarantees that a low actuation force is needed to perform the shape change. Yet the structure still has to maintain the capability to sustain structural and aerodynamic loads in spanwise direction. Corrugated structures are ideal candidates to fulfill these requirements.

It was found in other studies that for morphing wing applications low amplitude and low wavelength corrugation leads to the best aerodynamic performance [1], [4]. These attributes lead to larger thickness-to-periodic-length ratios, increasing interlaminar stresses and the risk of delamination.

For efficient analysis of anisotropic corrugated structures and detailed parameter studies simple numerically fast models are preferable since studies with commercial FEM software are limited due to enormous computational costs [5] if the considered structure contains many periods of the corrugation pattern and the laminate consists of many layers. Accordingly, several analytical models were suggested to calculate the initial stiffness of corrugated structures. Xia et al. [6] proposed an analytical homogenization model for orthotropic classical Kirchhoff plates to calculate the elements of the stiffness matrix on the principal diagonal valid for arbitrary corrugation geometries. The model was extended [7] for general balanced laminates, thus still ignoring the stiffness matrix B coupling bending and in-plane strain. Winkler et al. [8] presented analytical expressions for the analysis of equivalent orthotropic plates for circular sections. All these models are only valid for thin laminates and therefore not appropriate to calculate the stress distribution in thick corrugated laminates.

Peng et al. [9] presented a model to analyze the elastic stiffness behavior of trapezoidal and sinusoidal corrugations using a mesh-free Galerkin method. Liew et al. [10] extended the model to be used to calculate geometrical nonlinearities of corrugated structures.

Recently, Kress et al. [11] developed a finite-element model in order to linearly analyze an arbitrary laminate of arbitrary thickness with low computational costs. This approach is used in the present study and is extended in order to calculate the spatial stress distribution in the corrugated laminate cross-section.

The objective of this paper is to present a parameter study investigating the influence of geometry and anisotropy on through-thickness and shear stresses in corrugated structures made from anisotropic material. A sinusoidal shaped corrugation is compared to a corrugation consisting of circular sections. The studied parameters are laminate-thickness to periodic-cell-length ratio, material anisotropy degree, corrugation-amplitude to periodic-cell-length ratio. A full-factorial parameter study is performed in order to also investigate how the parameters influence each other. From the parameter study favorable configurations of corrugated sheets made from anisotropic materials shall be derived minimizing the interlaminar stresses and hence the risk of delamination.

The following section of the paper describes the numerical model and the load case followed by a description of the parameter study where the chosen parameters are introduced in detail. The next section presents the results including the stress solution of certain examples and the results of the parameter study. The paper closes with a discussion of the results and a conclusion.

2 MODEL AND LOAD CASE

In order to reduce the computational costs, a numerical FEM model that was suggested by Kress and Winkler [11], [12], [13] is used and extended in the present work. It uses a unit cell extending over one period of the corrugation pattern and the special planar finite element takes advantage of the generalized-plane strain state of the inner solution governing the interior of large corrugated sheets. The model was extended in order to calculate the local stresses from the strains using the constitutive law. These stress calculations were verified by checking the fulfillment of the mechanical equilibrium conditions such as the stress-free surfaces and were compared to FEM results of preliminary studies. Thanks to the low computational costs of one simulation this modeling approach is especially suitable for parameter studies where combinations of parameters and high resolution of parameter intervals are investigated.

The considered load case contained a forced displacement corresponding with a global strain of 1% in y-direction on the right edge of the unit cell while the left edge was fixed in y-direction as displayed in Figure 1. Both ends of the unit cells were coupled with periodic boundary conditions.

Figure 1: Load case for the parameter study

3 PARAMETER STUDY

To investigate the influence of geometry and anisotropy on the interlaminar stresses a parameter study was carried out for both the sinusoidal shape and the shape consisting of circular sections. As geometrical parameter the laminate-thickness to periodic-cell-length ratio (t/p) and the corrugation amplitude to periodic-cell-length ratio (h/p) were studied as described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Parameter definition

In order to examine the influence of the material anisotropy a degree of anisotropy k_a is defined as

$$k_a = \frac{E_s}{E_t} \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

where E_s and E_t denote Young's moduli of a transversely isotropic material along and perpendicular to the curved midface coordinate s , see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Coordinate system

The following parameter configurations were tested:

- $t/p = [0.02:0.02:0.1]$
- for circular section: $h/p = [0:0.05:0.75]$, for sinusoidal shape: $h/p = [0:0.05:0.35]$
- $k_a = [1:10:71]$

For the sinusoidal shape less h/p configurations were tested in order to avoid an unfeasible curvature in the shape.

For illustration the smallest and largest t/p configurations are shown in Figure 4 with $h/p=0.25$.

Figure 4: t/p configurations

The material parameters are based on a T300/Epoxy composite and listed in the following table:

$E_2 = E_3$	7000	MPa
$G_{31} = G_{12}$	5000	MPa
$G_{23} =$	$\frac{E_2}{2(1 + \nu_{23})}$	MPa
$\nu_{23} = \nu_{12}$	0.3	-
ν_{31}	0.27	-

Table 1: Material properties

Thanks to the numerical efficiency of the used modelling approach the parameter study was designed as a full factorial investigation.

4 RESULTS

The through-thickness stress distribution for the configuration $h/p = 0.25$, $t/p = 0.04$, $k_a = 1$ is illustrated in Figure 5. For the same configuration the shear stress is shown in Figure 6.

Through-thickness stress

Figure 5: Through-thickness stress for a) the circular sections and b) the sinusoidal shape using the parameters $h/p = 0.25$, $t/p = 0.04$, $k_a = 1$

Shear stress

Figure 6: Transverse shear stress for a) the circular sections and b) the sinusoidal shape using the parameters $h/p = 0.25$, $t/p = 0.04$, $k_a = 1$

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the results of the parameter study. The axes show the investigated parameters h/p , t/p and k_a . The colors refer to the level of interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratio as shown in the legends. Figure 7 illustrates the maximum through-thickness stress to the σ_s ratio for each parameter configuration where σ_s denotes the stress in s direction according to the coordinate system defined in Figure 3. Figure 8 shows the maximum shear stress to σ_s ratio for each configuration. As we can see from Figure 5 and Figure 6 we expect the maximum value for the through-thickness stress where the midplane is at maximum amplitude and the maximum shear stress at $z = 0$. The results show that through-thickness stresses are higher in the sinusoidal corrugation due to the higher curvature at the location of the maximum value.

In Figure 7 it can be seen that the maximum through-thickness stress to σ_S ratio increases for higher t/p and decreases for higher k_a values for both the sinusoidal and the circular corrugation. For the circular sections we can see that the maximum through-thickness stress to σ_S ratio increases for higher amplitude until a value of $h/p=0.25$ is reached which implies semi-circles and decreases again for higher amplitudes.

Figure 8 illustrates that the maximum shear stress to σ_S ratio increases for higher amplitudes and higher thickness and slightly decreases for higher k_a values.

Figure 7: Maximum through-thickness stress to σ_S ratio

Figure 8: Maximum shear stress to σ_s ratio

5 DISCUSSION

The parameter study shows that favorable configurations minimizing shear stress are achieved using high amplitudes. The through-thickness stress increases for the sinusoidal configuration for higher amplitudes. This is explained with the fact that the curvature at the location of the maximum through-thickness stress increases with increasing amplitudes. For the circular sections the through-thickness to σ_s ratios are much smaller than for the sinusoidal shape since the curvatures where the midplane is at

maximum amplitude are generally lower for the circular sections. A minimal value can be found for very large amplitude where the two sections almost consist of two full circles. Independent from the amplitude and the degree of anisotropy the interlaminar stresses always increase with increasing thickness. The interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratios also increase for higher degrees of anisotropy since in that case the in-plane stresses σ_5 can bear more loads.

Table 2 shows recommended configurations to minimize interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratio. For the sinusoidal shape the optimal configurations considering through-thickness stress is different from the configuration considering shear stress. Hence, in the design of sinusoidal shapes there is a need to find a compromise between shear and through-thickness stress. For the circular sections we find a configuration with high amplitudes and almost two full circles as a good solution for low interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratio. This configuration is favorable for both the through-thickness and shear stresses. Although, this configuration might have a mass penalty on one hand, it has a large bending stiffness around the y-axis on the other hand.

Configurations with lowest interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratios			
Circular sections		Sinusoidal shape	
Through-thickness stress	Shear stress	Through-thickness stress	Shear stress
$h/p=0.75, t/p=0.02, k_a=71$	$h/p=0.75, t/p=0.02, k_a=71$	$h/p=0.05, t/p=0.02, k_a=71$	$h/p=0.35, t/p=0.02, k_a=71$

Table 2: Optimal configurations concerning interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratio

In other studies it was found that corrugations with lower amplitudes perform aerodynamically better than such with high amplitudes [1], [4]. Therefore, we could also imagine that the found circular sections behave aerodynamically well, since they can be seen as corrugations with very small amplitudes as indicated in Figure 9 with the blue line.

Figure 9: Suggestion for aerodynamical performance as indicated with the blue line

6 CONCLUSION

A parameter study was presented investigating the influence of geometry and anisotropy on the interlaminar stresses for sinusoidal shapes and shapes consisting of circular sections. To be able to perform a full-factorial study a numerically efficient two-dimensional model was chosen that uses a unit-cell approach. It was applied to simulate a global in-plane loading across the corrugation for several configurations with different thickness, amplitude and degree of anisotropy. In the parameter study both the through-thickness stress and shear stress was analysed and compared to the stress along the midface-line.

The stress distribution shows a maximum through-thickness stress where the midplane is at maximum amplitude and a maximum shear stress at $z = 0$ as expected. For the sinusoidal shapes we can generally see higher through-thickness stress values since the curvature is higher at the point where the maximum stress occurs. In general, the interlaminar to intralaminar stress ratio increases for higher thicknesses and lower degrees of anisotropy.

For the circular sections high amplitudes implying more than a semi-circle are recommendable. For the sinusoidal shape high amplitudes seem to be suitable in order to reduce shear stresses, while with low amplitudes also low through-thickness stress can be achieved. In general, interlaminar stresses are higher for larger thicknesses and lower degrees of anisotropy.

From the parameter study we can derive favourable geometries for the corrugations. In case of the circular sections cross sections can be recommended that consists of almost two full circles. In case of the sinusoidal shapes an appropriate design lies between a low amplitude where through-thickness stresses decrease and high amplitude where shear stresses decrease.

We can conclude that the found desirable midface shapes achieve the goal of minimizing the interlaminar stresses for corrugated laminates of arbitrary thickness. Hence, we can directly use them to design corrugated sheets with a low risk of delamination. The used models are valid for arbitrary geometries and laminates. Therefore, future studies will investigate the failure risk for typical lay-ups and more midface geometries. Furthermore, the implementation of the favourable geometries in morphing wing applications can be considered regarding structural and aerodynamically aspects.

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